

LEGAL MEASURES TO INCREASE THE ATTRACTIVENESS OF THE TERRITORY'S INVESTMENT ENVIRONMENT

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The creation and improvement of the investment environment of the regions, ensuring its attractiveness, depends primarily on the legal conditions of the investment environment. It should be said that Uzbekistan has created a base of legal documents aimed at creating a favorable investment environment for the economy of the entire country and regions, including direct foreign investment, and protecting the legal rights and interests of investors and business units.

This aspect means that it is necessary to pay attention to such factors as developing the investment environment in all respects and increasing its attractiveness. In this regard, it is known from the historical experience of the developed and developing countries, especially the Central Asian countries, that the legal reforms carried out served to create a favorable investment environment for investors, or on the other hand, prevented the flow of investment into the country's economy.

"Comprehensive organization of investigative activity depends on its level of legal protection. Over the past years, a number of measures have been taken to create a favorable investment environment for attracting direct investment, and for the cooperative operation of enterprises with foreign investments. However, a number of legislation on invetction caused some complications in the practice of law enforcement. More precisely, the fact that most of the procedures related to the activity of invectition and the protection of the rights of foreign inventors are scattered and regulated by several laws, most of the provisions are repeated, and some important matters are defined not only by law, but also by statutes and guidelines, and there is some inconsistency between them¹.

In this regard, among the laws that are aimed at increasing the attractiveness of the investment environment of the regions, which are widely used in practice at the moment, the Decree-Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated August 25, 2015 "On Investment and Mutual Funds", Decree-Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated December 25, 2019 598-con "On Invectives and Invective Activities", O'RQ-205-con dated April 6, 2009 "On Ratification of the

¹ <https://uza.uz/uz/posts/investitsiya-faoliyatini-u-u-iy-tartibga-solishning-yaxhlit--03-02-2020>

Agreement between the Republic of Uzbekistan and Japan on the Liberalization, Promotion and Protection of Investments (Tashkent, August 15, 2008) ", Laws O'RQ-537-con of May 10, 2019 "On State-Economic Partnership", O'RQ-604-con of February 17, 2020 "On Compulsory Economic Zones" were adopted.

According to its structure, the Law "On Investments and Investment Activities" consisting of 12 chapters and 69 articles was further improved with new procedures and rules that did not exist in the previous legislation on investments. In this regard, the year 2019 of the Republic of Uzbekistan

The Law of December 25 O'RQ-598-con "On Investments and Investment Activities" is significant because it "regulates relationships in the field of investments and investment activities carried out by foreign and local investors." However, this Law does not include relations with centralized investments.

Benefits on taxes and fees are granted in accordance with the law. The preferences used for the state support of the considered investments and investment activities are in accordance with the decisions of the Council of Ministers of the Republic of Karakalpakstan, governors of the regions and the city of Tashkent, including the budget of the Republic of Karakalpakstan in relation to municipal objects, the decisions of the governors of the regions and the city of Tashkent. can be given with Privileges and preferences are given to investors who intend to make investments in the respective area based on the level of development of the infrastructure of the area. There are special powers to apply special tax benefits to enterprises specializing in production (providing services) in economic sectors, which are organized with the attraction of foreign direct investment and are approved by legal documents, in accordance with the procedure established by the Tax Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan².

Chapter 68 of the Tax Code, i.e., "Specific powers of levying taxes on participants of special economic zones" is defined for the participants of the special economic zones where the investors are located. According to him, Article 473 of the Code clearly states "Terms of hospitality to the participants of Special Economic Zones". In particular, according to the volume of investments, the participants of special economic zones are granted tax benefits in the form of exemption from property tax, land tax and tax for the use of water resources for a period determined by the decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

² <https://davalik.uz/uz/menu/pravovaja-zaschita-i-lgoty-investorov>

There are taxpayers with different forms of ownership in the list of those who have a tax exemption. The list includes state enterprises, private business entities, joint ventures, joint stock companies and foreign companies. According to Cohalar, enterprises operating in mining, banking, transport, pharmaceutical, utility services, oil and gas production, energy, insurance, medicine, construction, recreation, sport and other areas benefited from the benefits. The most widely used type of tax relief is corporate income tax, of which 16,565 or 37.7% of households used the unit. The type of tax with the least benefit is eca profit tax, 772 of this benefit or 1.7% were used by the business sector³.

According to the decision PQ-72 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated December 31, 2021 "On the approval of the investment program of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2022-2026 and the introduction of new approaches and mechanisms for managing investment projects", a number of new mechanisms to ensure the attractiveness of the investment environment was introduced. According to it, a "central project management office coordinating the project management system for strategic investment projects" was established.

In general, in order to improve the investment environment in the regions, it is necessary to constantly improve the adopted legal regulations. As a result of this, it is possible to create a favorable investment environment for attracting investments to the economy of the regions, to ensure its attractiveness.

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³ <https://anti-corruption.uz/uz/item/2022/05/30/soliq-imiyozlari-va-preferentsiyalar-berilgan-subektlar-hamda-ular-tomonidan-tilangan-soliqlar-miqdori-togrisidagi-malumatlar-ochiqligi-taminlanmoqda>

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